

THE IMPACT OF DIVIDEND POLICY ON SHARE PRICE AN EVALUATE STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

Profit approach remains to be a point of wrangle about indeed after persistent inquire about held, which states the relationship of profit arrangement and stock cost behavior. This article tries to bring out a light on to the impact of profit arrangement on stock cost behavior of seven diverse banks and companies in India for a period from 2015-2019. The consider centers on the effect of profit arrangement on shareholders riches companies in India. In this ponder, we have chosen the test of 7 listed banks and companies. The information is collected for the period of 5 a long time from the money related year 2015-2019. In this think about it clarifies and calculates normal and different relationship investigation. This concludes that there's a net worth relationship between the factors.

Keywords: dividend, net worth, shareholders

INTRODUCTION:

This paper attempts to recognise on the impact of dividend policy on stock price behaviour of different industries of Indian market the main intention of the study companies are listed from several Industries like FMCG mining Industries under telecom services Industries etc in the year of dividend policy is a protocol to a company e utilizes to decide on how much the properties and by the company and how much portion is and is also guesses by the Dividend policy here are the two measures are examine That is dividend yield and dividend payout ratio with the aid of panel data analysis this paper derivate the secondary data that is collected from the BSE e process to elevate the significant level between Dividend policy and stock price of an industry a dividend is

a vital source of income to the investors in the organisations it is started the investor leadership of the company .

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Reference (1) 1P.G. Thirumagal and 2S. Vasantha in A Research Paper on Impact of Dividend Payout on Shareholders Wealth in Indian Industries explains that It was originate that dividend payout had significant negative impact on shareholders wealth for majority of the industries. There was considerable difference in share price between pre and post dividend announcement.

Reference (2) Study Of Dividend Policy And Its Effect On Market Value Of Shares Of Selected Banks In India by Dr. Vinay Kandpal, 2 Prof P C Kavidayal Assistant .For the reason of study the financial data from the period 2003-04 to 2012-13 of particular Indian banks (15 Public and 15 Private) would be worn The data would be analyzed using statistical tools like multiple regression technique, t test, the coefficient of determination (R²) and F-Value. The grades of the data analysis might reveal that that there is a significant effect of dividend policy on the share price of selected Indian Banks. The study is limited to a time period of 10 years and only selected Indian Banks. The result might modify if the time period and number of banks are extended.

Reference (3) Priyanka Ranawat Ph.D. Research Scholar, Rajasthan Vidhyapeeth in A STUDY ON DIVIDEND POLICY AND ITS IMPACT ON THE SHAREHOLDERS' WEALTH IN CEMENT INDUSTRIES explains that the cement companies have seen a net profit growth rate of 85 per cent. With this massive success, the cement industry in India has contributed almost 8 per cent to India's for its economic development. At the present time, the cement industry is increasing fast and to know, how the dividend policies of cement industries play a essential role on shareholders wealth. This research will analyze the dividend policy factors that affect the shareholders wealth.

Reference (4). Yanqiong Zhong School of Economics, Jinan University, Guangzhou, China on the topic is Analysis of Dividend Policy Influence Factors of China's Listed Banks Then the article analyse the factors affecting dividend policy of listed banks by via empirical method, and find that profitability and liquidity of assets have a positive effect on the dividend payment rate,

debt levels have a negative effect on the dividend payment rate, and the growth ability and operation ability have no considerable effect on the rate of dividend payment.

Reference (5) Hira Ahmad Master of Financial Economics Candidate University of Western Ontario is explains the Determinants of dividend policy: A study about the impact of changing firm characteristics on dividend payout ratios It was found that size and liquidity create statistically significant results in terms of having some relationship the dividend payout ratios of the firms. After performing the Granger-Causality test, it was resolute that only liquidity of the firm has some essential relationship with the dividend payout ratio of a firm.

Reference (6) Mudassar Hasan¹, Muhammad Ishfaq Ahmad², Muhammad Yasir Rafiq³, Ramiz Ur Rehman⁴ ¹Lahore Business School, The University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan is explains the topic Dividend Payout Ratio and Firm's Profitability. Evidence from Pakistan and the topic explains that the Firm performance is calculated by earning per share (EPS) and return on assets (ROA). The results of logarithmic regression demonstrate that no matter what industry is, there is a negative impact of dividend payout ratio on next year earnings of a firm.

Reference (7) M Kannadhasan, Indian Institute of Management Raipur S Aramvalarthan, Amrita School of Business P.Balasubramanian, Amrita School of Business Aishwarya Gopika, Amrita School of Business the topic is DETERMINANTS OF DIVIDEND POLICY OF INDIAN MANUFACTURING COMPANIES: PANEL AUTOREGRESSIVE DISTRIBUTED LAG ANALYSIS identifies that The study analyse the determinants of dividend policy of manufacturing companies in India with panel data. Financial leverage, profitability, and firm size verify the dividend policy of the firm. Development of the firm has an effect on dividend policy in the short run. To best of the awareness, no study has done on this topic using Panel ARDL in Indian context.

Reference (8) Brahmaiah Bezawada¹, Ravi Kumar Tati² ¹IICFAI Business School, IFHE, Hyderabad, India ²Manipal University, Dubai, UAE topic is Dividend Policy and Firm Valuation —A Study of Indian Electrical Equipment Manufacturing Industry analyses that This paper attempts to analyze whether the dividend policy of a firm affects the market value of a firm and

the shareholders' wealth. We have set our intention is to find out the impact of dividend policy on the shareholders' wealth in the Indian electrical equipment manufacturing industry. this study shown the empirical indication with some of the dividend insignificance theories such as M&M. The results indicate that there is a negative non-linear association between market value of a share and the dividend yields.

Reference (9) Adam Enebrand& Tobias Magnusson explains the topic is Dividend policy and its impact on firm valuation and The findings of this study specify that the stock price of high dividend yield firms are more dependent on financial performance compared to low dividend yield firms yet an on the whole positive correlation is found between financial performance and stock price for both samples.

Reference (10) Mobeen Ur Rehman¹ Aabid Hussain² the topic is IMPACT OF DIVIDEND POLICY ON PERFORMANCE OF FIRMS HAVING STOCKS LISTED IN AN EMERGING STOCK MARKET and explains. In this paper we have taken sample of 475 companies and the data is the secondary one. Ratios have been compute of all the companies that mainly find out the dividend policy and then the correlation tests have been run to see that whether the results are significant or not. In the conclusion they have mentioned the variables that play a major role in determining the performance of the firms.

Reference (11) PrathibhaThuvara Balasubramanian P Bhawana Jain are explains the topic that is Impact of Dividend Policy on Stock Return Behaviour and then explains . The result also shows that there is a positive important relation between stock return and earnings per share. It also showed there is a non-significant but negative relationship between the stock return and size of the firm. The yearly data has been composed from CMIE prowess for the years 2010-2015 for every industry.

Reference (12) Dinesh Kumar Sharma¹ and Ritu Wadhwa² and the topic is Ownership Structures and Dividend Policy - A Study of Bombay Stock Exchange-500 and The multiple regression analysis has been functional to the data to study the effect of shareholding pattern of the companies of BSE -500 on the dividend policy of respective companies. Only 457 companies could be

calculated due to lack of available information on one or the other variables in particular company. The result indicated that 6% of variation has been explained by the independent variables (promote, foreign institutional shareholding and institutional shareholding).

Reference (13) Syed Akif Shah¹, Umara Noreen² the topic is Stock Price Volatility and Role of Dividend Policy explains that. The study has originate major negative relationship between SPV and dividend policy variables i.e., DP and DY. Study has also found significant positive relationship between control variables (AG, EV and EPS) and SPV in KSE. But in case of the left over two control variables i.e., FS and LD, these were establish to be negatively related to SPV. The findings of this research are expected to contribute to dividend policy literature by provided that evidence from Pakistani stock market to prior studies done in developed and developing countries.

Reference (14) HirinduKawshala *, KushaniPanditharathna and the topic is The Effect of Dividend Policy on Corporate Profitability: An Empirical Study on Beverage, Food and Tobacco Industry in Sri Lanka and explains that . The purpose of this study is to discover the impact of dividend payout on corporate profitability in Sri Lanka. The dividend policy calculated using the dividend payout ratio, while return on equity (ROE) used as a measure of profitability. The study done that there is a positive significant relationship between dividend policy and the profitability in Beverage, Food & Tobacco (BFT) industry in Sri Lanka. The time horizon for this study is limited when compared with other studies.

Reference (15) Werner R. MurhadiUniversitas Surabaya and the topic is that Study On Dividend Policy: Antecedent and Its Impact On Share Price and explains Research finding indicates that signaling theory still related in influencing movement of share price. In addition, research finding also supports agency theory told by Jensen in shows the influence of free cash flow to share price. For the influence of structure of ownership to share price, the result supports entrenchment argument. While influence of structure of ownership to dividend policy found by result which do not support agency theory. Life Cycle theory in this research is obtained by result which is research verification before all, where there are influence of cycle step of company life to dividend policy.

Objectives of the Study

- The paper focuses on analyzing the effect of dividend announcement on the share price of selected Banks.

YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
YES bank	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+
2015	164.622	166.877	-2.255	165.674	166.449	-0.775	165.364	169.188	-3.824
2016	175.447	185.997	-10.55	172.457	187.975	-15.518	167.856	195.659	-27.803
2017	321.007	315.864	5.143	315.5	319.629	-4.129	306.621	304.134	2.487
2018	350.771	315.257	35.514	348.839	314.317	34.522	343.751	309.974	33.777
2019	247.857	168.52	79.337	257.553	158.035	99.518	256.4	150.728	105.672
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
ICICI bank	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+
2015	282.811	293.85	- 11.039	285.857	290.425	-4.568	290.167	283.687	6.48
2016	225.298	200.227	25.071	216.243	203.266	12.977	212.11	211.88	0.23
2017	249.227	272.636	- 23.409	251.357	275.538	-24.181	251.705	283.506	-31.801
2018	281.642	307.071	- 25.429	284.01	299.757	-15.747	281.903	293.481	-11.578
2019	400.721	381.278	19.443	398.753	392.639	6.114	396.046	407.975	-11.929
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
HDFC bank	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+

2015	1,335.68	1,307.96	27.72	1,332.96	1302.03	30.93	1,295.91	1,255.49	40.42
2016	1,350.76	1,307.63	43.13	1,359.22	1,272.89	86.33	1,359.94	1,251.86	108.08
2017	44.188	43.665	0.52	44.229	44.1971	0.03	43.525	46.1024	-2.58
2018	48.833	51.9699	-3.14	49.0707	51.81	-2.74	48.5816	52.6325	-4.05
2019	58.542	56.294	2.25	60.876	55.831	5.04	62.604	54.358	8.25
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
INFOSYS	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+
2015	7.79	7.81	-0.02	7.88	7.88	0.00	7.80	7.91	-0.11
2016	9.70	9.23	0.46	9.49	9.23	0.25	9.43	9.02	0.41
2017	7.6	7.6428	-0.04	7.5771	7.5671	0.01	7.422	7.5391	-0.12
2018	9.327	9.188	0.14	9.1992	9.371	-0.17	8.965	9.1663	-0.20
2019	10.522	10.61	-0.09	10.1128	10.727	-0.61	9.792	10.714	-0.92
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
SBI	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+
2015	286.25	276.54	9.71	277.48	266.835	10.64	279.36	264.05	15.31
2016	185.89	173.41	12.49	187.81	185.22	2.59	189.28	199.08	-9.81
2017	301.42	288.242	13.18	297.76	288.157	9.60	292.859	285.866	6.99
2018	246.67	247.742	-1.07	243.58	257.81	-14.23	247.989	266.208	-18.22
2019	311.921	307.578	4.34	314.01	309.21	4.80	307.198	330.153	-22.96
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
IBM	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+

2015	148.61	146.23	2.38	148.50	147.28	1.22	150.66	148.76	1.91
2016	158.23	153.08	5.15	160.21	152.18	8.02	162.55	154.20	8.35
2017	142.064	144.611	-2.55	141.786	145.511	-3.72	142.948	150	-7.05
2018	121.69	118.76	2.93	120.55	122.84	-2.29	120.01	135.061	-15.05
2019	134.72	145.16	-10.44	133.6	147.76	-14.16	137.13	144.35	-7.22
YEARS/DAYS	7 DAYS			14 DAYS			30 DAYS		
TCS	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+	PRE	POST	-/+
2015	1,278.40	1,304.95	-26.55	1,276.41	1,294.38	-17.97	1,278.96	1,271.31	7.65
2016	1,192.30	1,191.60	0.70	1,154.60	1,194.70	-40.10	1,124.80	1,941.17	-816.37
2017	1,215.40	1,285.42	-70.02	1197.6	1,285.00	-87.40	1,202.14	1,239.06	-36.92
2018	1,864.00	1,936.52	-72.52	1,891.94	2,025.32	-133.38	1,904	2,068.25	-164.37
2019	2,007.90	2,133.70	- 125.80	2,130.10	2188.7	-58.60	2,177	2,215.78	165.36

Hypothesis Formation:

- Ho: There is a significant effect of dividend announcement on the share price.

Model Selection

Taking into consideration the objective of the study, mean and regression analysis is best suited for the analysis and the same is used for data analysis. Normalization of the data was done before using the regression model.

Research Methodology

Study period and sample selection:

For the purpose of this study financial data of Indian banks [public and private]and companies from 2015 to 2019 was taken. This period included recession and post-recession period Private and public banks and companies listed on NSE were taken for the study on the basis of following criteria's:

- Availability of data for continuous period of 5 years
- Continuous dividend payments for 5 years

The banks finally considered for the study are YES bank, ICICI bank, HDFC bank SBI, and companies are Infosys, IBM TCS.

DATA ANALYSIS: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the table 1 we can observe that the dividend values of yes bank there is a positive value in 7 days and 14 days, there is a negative value shows in 30 days. The ICICI bank the dividend value is positive in 7 and 14 days, and it shows negative value in 30 days. The HDFC bank shows the dividend value in negative in 7 days and 14 days and also in 30 days.

Infosys company shows the dividend values in 7 days and 14 days are negative prices. where as in 30 days the values are represented in a positive way. SBI dividend values are between 7 and 14 days represent the negative values where as in 30 days it represents positive values.

Here ,the IBM company dividend values represent the positive value in 7 days and 14.where as in 30 days it also represents a positive value. The TCS company shows the dividend values in 7 and 14 days and also in 30 days it represents the positive values.

Table2: correlation

<i>TICKER</i>		<i>PRE- EVENT</i>	<i>POST- EVENT</i>
<i>YESBAN K</i>	<i>PRE</i>	1	-0.17137
	<i>POS T</i>	-0.17137	1
<i>ICICI</i>	<i>PRE</i>	1	0.142924

<i>TICKER</i>		<i>PRE- EVENT</i>	<i>POST- EVENT</i>
<i>HDFC</i>	<i>PRE</i>	1	-0.50115
	<i>POS T</i>	-0.50115	1
	<i>PRE</i>	1	-0.20481

	POS			INFOSYS	POS		
	T	0.142924	1	S	T	-0.20481	1
	PRE	1	0.71811		PRE	1	-0.57475
SBI	POS			TCS	POS		
	T	0.71811	1		T	-0.57475	1

Here the table 2 represent the correlation values in the dividend share price of different banks and companies. The yes bank represents the value below the zero, i.e. -0.17137 .so it is called as negative correlation. The ICICI bank shows the positive correlation value i.e., 0.142924, then it is also a positive correlation. SBI correlation value is above the zero i.e, 0.71811 so it is a positive correlation. The HDFC bank represents the negative correlation -0.50115. The Infosys company represents the negative correlation the value is -20481. The TCS company represents the value i.e. -0.57475, so it is called as a negative correlation.

CONCLUSION

Profit payout had a negative effect on shareholders riches for all selected industries together from 2015 to 2019, all chosen businesses together from 20015 to 2015.Dividend payout proportion had significant negative effect on lion's share of chosen businesses and advertise capitalizations. Payment of more profit would diminish the shareholders riches. Dividend payout had positive effect on shareholders riches for all chosen businesses little capitalization companies It was found that dividend announcement affect on the closing share cost of the companies was more favourable amid post occasion for all chosen businesses and advertise capitalization than the pre occasion and occasion. It was found that there was networth distinction in closing share between pre and post occasion for all chosen businesses large capitalization companies

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